

On the Geometric Substitution Cipher, the Eight Concealment Tricks, and the Underlying Language of Voynich Manuscript

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Abstract.

For nearly six centuries, the decipherment of Voynich Manuscript has baffled scholars and cryptologists. None of the previous attempts succeeded to find out the used coding method in this manuscript; hence, scholars called it the world's most mysterious book. This work, therefore, explains the design of its cipher and identifies its underlying language. It demonstrates the mathematical idea and the method of "design by addition" that an anonymous proficient designer has used in order to create over one hundred glyphs, using strokes, circles, and half circles. It proves that this designer used the grid of the rectangle 6*8 units and its diagonal of 10 units to create glyphs so that each denotes numerically the rank of a specific letter in *Abjd* (*Abjad*) sequence, from one to twenty-eight. It shows as well that the designer used eight concealment tricks as extra measures, which include the partial polyalphabetic substitution of seven *Abjd* ranks, deleting most of the prepositions and conjunction words, and changing the positions of words in each sentence, in order to conceal the geometric cipher and the encoded language. Then, based on the transliteration and translation of the introductory paragraph, in addition to six sentences and a hundred words from different pages, this work proves that the underlying language of the manuscript is the medieval Hindi of Hindustan. The translation samples demonstrate that the manuscript appears to contain Indian folklore chatters about, e.g., path of the banyan trees, the jackal and the partridge, and the lake of surprises, etc., which are narrated by the idols that metaphorically represent the beloved women in the Hindustani culture; and its writer's nickname is Bido.

Keywords: Voynich Manuscript, MS-408, VMS, Idris, Hermes, Geometric Substitution Cipher, Hindustan, Urdu, Hindi.

1. Introduction

The Voynich Manuscript (VMS) is a 15th century codex (Layfield *et al*, 2020), where in 2009, the result of carbon-14 dating experiment showed that its leather-parchments were produced between 1404 and 1438 CE (Zyats *et al*, 2012; Zandbergen, 2016). The digital numbering, from f.1r to f.116v, of the digitized copy of VMS¹ demonstrate that it originally had 232 pages of various sizes, and twenty-eight pages of which are missing (Davis, 2020); but without discovering the coding method, this does not confirm that the current VMS's text is incomplete. Almost ninety percent of the remained pages contain colored illustrations with handwritten text. Most illustrations are sketches of plants that might be medical, anesthetic, or just fictional portraits (e.g., f.2v); some were drawn in a surreal way, which depict plant leaves as silhouettes of birds (e.g. f.56r) and roots of plants as imaginary marine-creatures, animals, or human faces (e.g. f.55v, f.90v, & f.101v). VMS contains as well diagrams that seem similar

¹ - See the online digital copy of VMS at (<https://collections.library.yale.edu/pdfs/2002046.pdf>).

to the astrological and astronomical charts in medieval esoteric books (e.g., f.67r), sketches of naked women disport in what look like natural lakes down a waterfall or rainy zippers, or in constructed reservoirs on a water stream (f.75r), fictional flying bathtubs (f.82r), and few men (e.g., f.66r & f.80r). In few pages we also see rough sketches of animals such as a pangolin (f.80v), a serpent (f.49r), a horse, a deer, a jackal, a komodo dragon, a giant catfish (f.79v), a bird like a falcon (f.86v), and a dragon (f.25v), as well as what looks like an elf or a statue below a blue rose (f.102r). The foldout page f.85v-f.86r demonstrates what appears as an imaginary schematic site-plan of a group of castles and temples in a mountainous area with cardinal directions and a text, in the southern (or northern) corner, written in a spiral form similar to the ancient technique of writing the spiritual sentences in Hermetic sciences. This page also shows the use of the architecture technique of façade and axonometric rotation—in the projection plan—in different directions, the free-hand presentation technique of contour lines and the floor of the outdoor spaces, accurate parallel grid, and sunrise/sunset during the equinoxes, which indicates that it was produced by an architect, may be knowledgeable in spherical astronomy. He also symbolized the direction of north (or south) with a small circle around a triangular glyph from an ancient list of secret writing scripts, which indicates that he might have studied *Šimiyā σημεία*, i.e., spiritual secret writings (see Al-Simāwi², 1260 CE, pp.41-46). The sequence of illustrations in VMS directs the mind to unproved hypothesis regarding that it discusses diverse subjects grouped in separate sections; there are many opinions regarding this hypothesis, for instance, outside the framework of any intended spiritual scenario, Bauer (1917, p.8) said, it is possible that the pictures are not actually related to the text. Yet, in terms of creativity, and from the metaphysical perspective, the surreal pun technique used by the painter depicts the latent spirit in each botanical element presented in the artwork to incarnate—in the botanical realm—perhaps part of the philosophy of Socrates in dialogue Phaedo (Plato, 330 BCE-a). Alternatively, it may be an incarnation of part of the secret philosophy of divination—using seeds of plants—in some ancient cultures in Africa and Mesoamerica, e.g., Maya. In the eye of any literate painter and student of the ancient metaphysical philosophies, the illustrations in general—with the like chemical bottles in, e.g., page f.88r—may give the impression that it discusses spiritual practices and the relevant cures and advices. It may be similar to the instructions that are usually included without pictures of plants or humans in medieval esoteric books that show as well the desirable actions in the course of time (Al-Buni, 1226 CE, p.218, & p.363).

A set of contents with seductive illustrations that make it looks tempting to be acquired, with expensive price, in the eyes of many people before the era of imprinting, informatics, and internet. Without decoding the cipher, no one can affirm which information the manuscript includes: scientific theories, fictional narratives, or obscure traditions; nor can confirm what type of text is this: prose, verse, or magical spells; and no one knows yet who wrote it. However, there is partly reliable information about some of those who interacted with its contents mentally, sensorically, or spiritually and kept it in their possessions during this long period, until Wilfrid Voynich purchased it from the Jesuit library in Rome in 1912; and it was named after him ever since. From among the previous owners (see, Robinson, 2016), the first known buyer (in 1599 CE) was Rudolf II, Holy Roman Emperor (Guzy, 2022) and the last known student of this cipher manuscript (in 1666 CE) was the Jesuit polymath Athanasius Kircher (Steele, 1928). Perhaps all interested researchers, and the author too (from the first look in a news in January 13, 2023), cannot deny that there is something unusual in VMS—like mirage—that attracts the mind to approach it in order to investigate its identity and contents; at least the artistic design of its glyphs. Since 1969, it has been kept in Yale University's Beinecke rare books and manuscripts library, with a catalog number MS-408 (Robinson, 2016). All attempts by experts during the 20th century, including those by known code-breakers from WWI and WW2 (e.g., William Friedman, Elizabeth Friedman, Prest Currier, and John Tillman) and their supporting teams were not

²- The book cover is missing, but the author mentioned his name in page 26, and the publication date may be during the 13th century.

successful to find out the used coding method in VMS (D’Imperio, 1978); yet, they produced comprehensive studies on this enigmatic conundrum. During the last two decades, arrays of researches have been published on the topic too, which included advanced computer analyses, diverse claims, and some interesting findings. Some scholars concluded that VMS is, or might be, a hoax, i.e., it was not produced by encoding of a human language (e.g., Whitfield, 2003; Rugg, 2004; Schinner, 2007; Rugg & Taylor, 2017) and its text is statistically similar to human produced samples of meaningless text (Gaskell & Bower, 2022). Other works showed statistical proofs indicate that the characteristics of VMS’s text resemble that of the human languages (e.g., Landini, 2001; Bower & Lindemann, 2021) and five scribes participated in writing the text (Davis, 2020 & 2022). All published or announced hypotheses³ regarding the underlying language of VMS were not based on decoding its true cipher; hence, no one has provided the correct decoding method for transliterating the whole set of glyphs in VMS. Regarding the encoded script, from among the published researches, one explanation was found consistent with the second result of the present work, which relied on analyzing the text by computer. That is, regarding the results of determining what might be vowels, and their locations, in the words of VMA, Reddy and Knight (2011) pointed out that a more likely explanation, of the results, is that the script is an *Abjd* (*Abjad*). Yet, their conclusion hints to that —*Abjd* system and— VMA’s text do not contain vowels, which may not be true.

In fact, VMS was written using special forms of glyphs that, despite the use of advanced computer analysis operations, formed a strong and unexpected barrier against identifying its underlying language. The reason most likely concerns the obscure image which seems latent behind designing the contents of VMS and the related Ethno-mathematics that the designer of its glyphs seem was aware about and used it to create the coding method of VMS’s text. Unless the encryption was for hiding some obscure traditions, this situation may call for thinking that in this obscure realm, especially in the medieval and pre-Renaissance eras, the primary purpose of VMS may have two sides. It has a deceptive goal and an intelligent goal in the same time. The first targets the treasure of physical gold and the latter targets the treasure of lost knowledge or culture. Even if the deceptive side was for selling nothing more than gibberish, the intelligent side is probably there in the form of a competition to unravel the puzzle. The evidence of the intelligent side is written in VMS, as will be demonstrated in section-2 herein below, which may have unforeseen purpose. Therefore, this work primarily deals with the intelligent side in order to show the method of designing the cipher and the glyphs of VMS in section-2, and then to identify its underlying language in section-3. Discussing what the full text of VMS contains is outside the scope of this work. Just the translation of the first paragraph, six sentences, and a hundred words from different pages will be discussed in section-4 in order to show the reliable evidences regarding its underlying language, and to give a glimpse about the VMS’s core topic.

2. The expandable geometric cipher of VMS (MS-408).

One of the basic principles of the ancient Egyptian Ethno-mathematics of Idris (Al-Buni⁴, 1226 CE, p.370), the so-called Hermes Trismegistus that the Greeks identified as Thoth⁵ (Manetho, 3rd century BCE, p.209; Chambers, 1882, p.vii; Ebeling, 2007, pp.45-48; & Von Stuckrad, 2009, p.55), is the use of numbers to denote the alphabetical letters. In this ancient field, each letter has two numeric values, following two different reckoning systems. In the first system, the numeric value represents the

³- See for instance the hypotheses of Bax, Hauer, Kondark, Gibbs, & Cheshire in the review of Bower & Lindemann (2021).

⁴- See a copy of Al-Buni’s book in Arabic at (<https://collections.library.yale.edu/catalog/32304220>); and there are some attempts to translate the book into other languages, see for example the Spanish translation of some parts of the book by Cordero, J. C. at (<https://archive.org/details/al-buni/page/368/mode/1up>).

⁵- According to Socrates in dialogue Phaedrus, Thoth is the inventor of —priestly— writing (Plato, 330 BCE-b).

rank (collation) of each letter in *Abjd* sequence of the tribes of Madian in Sinai (Al-Maqrizi, 1442 CE, vol.1, p.525) that contains 28 un-compounded letters, where *A,b,j,d* (or *A,b,g,d*) are the first four letters in the sequence. *Abjd* ranks have multiple types of interpretation related to the domain of use. For instance, in simple geometry, each *Abjd* rank can be interpreted as the number of uniform linear intervals that a letter denotes on the scale from one to twenty-eight units, as the 28 mean-fingers of the ancient Egyptian royal cubit⁶. In the second system, the numeric value represents the circular travel distance that each of the 28 letters implies on the scale, of variable intervals, from one to a thousand arc degrees (i.e., from 1° to 2 cycles and 280°), but, in the mind of many people, *Abjd* (*Abjad*) values of the second system are used in an abstract way. This work proves that the designer of the cipher of VMS used the first system, i.e., the ranks of *Abjd* sequence.

Based on a review of the full text of VMS —thanks to Yale University for publishing a digital copy online⁷— the author found that it contains almost 78 forms of glyphs. According to design theories and principles in the realm of architecture and fine arts, these glyphs were not designed by transformation from the script of any other writing system, using for instance the methods of abstraction, subtraction, twisting, stretching, flipping, and/or rotation around an axis. In VMS, the only used method is "design by addition", using circles, half circles, and vertical, horizontal, and/or inclined strokes. In history, the method of designing symbols by addition of strokes was used to create the ancient Egyptian hieratic numerals (Aboulfotouh, 2012). It was based on the use of a grid of squares (1*1 unit) within a rectangle 3*4 units —equivalent to two of the right-angle triangles 3-4-5— and its diagonal of 5 units as geometric intervals to create the shapes of the hieratic numeral signs. The designer of VMS’s glyphs used the same method to create signs that denote the numeric ranks of letters of an unknown alphabet. He used the grid of the rectangle 6*8 units —equivalent to two of the ancient Egyptian right-angle triangle 6-8-10 (Aboulfotouh, 2019)— and its diagonal of 10 units as geometric intervals to create the shapes of the glyphs of VMS, as illustrated in fig.1.

Figure.1: The method of generating the geometric elements for assembling VMS’s glyphs: (i) in the rectangle *ABED*, the sides *AD* and *AB* equal 6 and 8 units, respectively; and the diagonal *AE* in green color equals 10 units; hence, it denotes ten, (ii) each of the half circles, in light-blue and purple colors, has a diameter of one unit; hence, each denotes one, (iii) each vertical or horizontal side of a grid unit —in purple color— denotes one, (iv) the rectangles *BCFE*, *EFIH*, and *DEHG* are similar to the rectangle *ABED*; each of their diagonals denotes ten, and (v) in the rectangle *BCFE*, both *CJ* and *JE* is half *CE*, in green color, and equals 5 units; hence, each of their corresponding circles, in red and yellow colors, denotes five.

⁶- See the design of the Egyptian royal cubit in (Aboulfotouh, 2015 & 2022).

⁷- See MS-408 or VMS’s pages at (<https://collections.library.yale.edu/mirador/2002046>).

The first 10 columns in table.1 demonstrate the design of 44 glyphs from almost 78 glyphs of VMS. These columns show how each of these glyphs was assembled by the addition of some of the eight design elements that each denotes, or has, a numerical value in units. Specifically, as also shown in fig.1, half a circle of one unit diameter denotes "1", a vertical or horizontal stroke of one unit of length denotes "1", a circle with a diameter of five units denotes "5", and an inclined stroke of ten units of length denotes "10". For instance, as shown in fig.2a, the designer of the cipher assembled the glyph of rank 13 by using two circles that each has a diameter of 5 units and three strokes that each is one unit of length. Similarly, each of the other glyphs in VMS was created to denote the corresponding rank in an aesthetic way.

Figure.2: Example of assembling the glyphs in VMS, (a) Initial form of the glyph of rank 13 (left), and (b) its final aesthetic form after rescaling the design elements by reducing (topological compression) the diameters of the two circle and increasing (topological stretching) the lengths of the two vertical elements (right).

The coding method that the designer decided to use can be called the “Expandable Geometric Substitution Cipher”, (EGSC). The term “Expandable” here implies that it has no limit, in terms of both the number of glyphs and the number of applications using diverse sequences of the alphabets of diverse human languages.

In handwriting, the designer used eight concealment tricks as additional security measures in order to conceal the geometric cipher and the underlying language; where the first four tricks secure the idea of the geometric cipher. The *first concealment trick* is that the design elements that assemble the glyphs were not drawn in accurate proportions. Each element was rescaled to an appropriate size to create a consistent aesthetic shape and make the eye aware only about how many circles, half circles, or strokes are included in each letter’s glyph in order to recognize its rank and identity. This was done by topologically rescaling (i.e., to decrease by compression or to increase by stretching) the diameters of the circles (each denotes 5) and half circles (each denotes one) and using diverse lengths of vertical and horizontal strokes (each denotes one). The term topologically rescaling here implies that the numeric value of each deformed (rescaled) design element doesn’t change by the effect of compression or stretching. See for instance the final form of the glyph of rank 13 in fig.2b. This smart-idea created additional security against quick decipherment, because the forms of some created glyphs became similar to the script of some known alphabets or numeral signs but have different pronunciations or meanings. For instance, as shown in table.1, the glyphs of ranks 1 and 5 look like the letters *c* and *o* in Latin, respectively; and the glyphs of ranks 6, 10 and 11 look like the Arabic numerals 9, 8, and 2, respectively.

To read the ranks of the complex glyphs in a quick way, such as the glyph of rank 28 (table.1) —that look like the ancient wooden-cranes of megalithic construction— we can count the number of vertical strokes from left to right, then we count the number of horizontal strokes top-down, followed by counting the number of half circles, and finally, we add the values of circles. The intersection of any two strokes does not imply splitting each one of them into two strokes. What has been taken into account is only the change of direction and not the intersection. The ranks of all glyphs used in VMS are from 1 to 28. There are also few glyphs with higher numerical values, e.g., 61 (f.42v), which seem artistic and not alphabetical (or perhaps, each was designed using *Abjd*'s circular travel distances, i.e., the *Abjad* values in the abstract sense in order to denote numbers in the text).

Moreover, some glyphs in VMS denote similar ranks, which indicates that each of the corresponding letters may have multiple pronunciations, e.g., the ranks 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 11, and 10. The designer also created —more than— 30 compound-glyphs (e.g., see table.2) that each one combines two or three letters in one glyph form. Besides, eight of the 78 glyphs look like some *Sīmiyā* symbols, but their designs follow the same assembling method; only two of them were used in words, such as one of the cases of rank 21 (see table.1). The remaining 6 glyphs may have been used in the 28 missing pages; and due to this limitation, their ranks were not verified, which were reckoned based on the assumption that each inclined stroke denotes ten. So far, the body of VMS's text was produced (written) using almost 72 glyphs and 30 compound glyphs, i.e., 102 glyphs in total. Table.2 shows the 108 glyphs of VMS. These glyphs are what have been found in VMS until the date of submitting this paper for publication; but there may be other glyphs have fallen inadvertently, particularly in drawings, and the reader can easily identify the rank and identity of each, using the above-mentioned method.

Regarding the intelligent side, in the left margin of page f.49v, the scribe wrote two columns. The 1st column is comprised of a set of five Arabic numerals from 1 to 5 written top-down and linked to a set of five glyphs (with ranks 5, 2, 6, 1, & 1, respectively) from the 26 glyphs in the 2nd column. As shown in fig.3, in the two sets, the total sum of either the five numerals, or the ranks of the five glyphs is 15; and 7 is the total sum of the 3rd and 4th values in both sets. Besides, the 2nd values are the same in the two sets, and the 1st and 5th values in the numeral set meet the 5th and 1st values in the set of 5 glyphs, respectively. The scribe also wrote the Arabic numeral 2 above the glyph of rank 2 in a word in page f.24v (see table.3), which is the only case of using Arabic numerals in VMS's text; the other cases are found only in margins. The partial decoding key in fig.3 indicates that the designer did not have the intention to prevent strangers from breaking the cipher. On the contrary, he did it as a puzzle that can be solved by others. It is worth mentioning here that D'Imperio (1978, p.37) pointed out that the published works of Brumbaugh was based on the hypothesis that the sequences in the margins in f.1r, f.49v, f.66r, and f.76r; and in the 2nd ring in f.57v, as well as in the sequence in f.116v can provide aid in penetrating the cipher of VMS. Yet, unfortunately, his analyses —as demonstrated by D'Imperio— are irrelevant to the old idea of ranks of letters in an alphabet.

Links between the two sets	Set of 5 Numerals	Set of 5 Glyphs	
		Glyph	Rank
1 st No# meets the last glyph of rank 1	1	◦	5
2 nd No# meets the glyph of rank 2	2	ꞥ	2
3+4=7 & 6+1=7	3	᠑	6
	4	◌	1
5 th No# meets the 1 st glyph of rank 5	5	᠔	1
Total	15	Total	15

Figure.3: Key of the Geometric Substitution Cipher of VMS (MS-408, f.49v).

The fact that VMS includes twenty-eight ranks of letters partly refutes the claims that the encrypted alphabet contains a number of letters fewer than this range. The languages that are based on 28 ranks of letters are those of the countries that use Arabic or Persian script, i.e., most of the countries that were within the jurisdiction of the Islamic Caliphate during the 7th and 8th centuries CE. Today, in these countries the current used collation of letters is different from that of the ancient *Abjd* sequence of Sinai. Unfortunately, by the end of the 7th century CE, *Nasr ibn Asim al-laythi*, an Arabic grammarian from Basra, changed it into *Abtṣ* sequence that still be used until today, which is based on placing the letters that look similar in shape beside each other⁸. He changed the collation of 26 letters excluding the first two; for instance, the letter *t* of rank 22 became the 3rd in *Abtṣ* sequence. In this regard, the *Abjd* sequence of Morocco⁹ was also taken into consideration. Hence, to test the two *Abjd* sequences, it was taken into account that the palaces of six letters (with ranks: 15, 18, 21, 26, 27, 28) in the *Abjd* sequence of Morocco are different from the original *Abjd* sequence of Sinai. Besides, in this enigmatic case, using the *Abtṣ* sequence of *Nasr ibn Asim al-laythi*, will never lead to identifying the underlying language of VMS. Apparently, the designer of the glyphs relied on this, **second concealment trick** in order to reinforce his cipher against quick decipherment by those who are not aware of the use of ranks of letters in the ancient Ethno-mathematics of Idris. Besides, the change of the last stroke into a curve in the glyphs of the letter ranks 6, 20, 21, 22, 25, and 26 (see table.1 and table.2) represents the **third concealment trick** in order to secure the idea of the geometric cipher.

3. The underlying language of VMS (MS-408).

Using diverse online translation portals —thanks to their services— the author then tested a selection of words from different pages of VMS (either from the text or written beside the illustrations) in order to identify its underlying language. After long process of trial and error, using Roman and Perso-Arabic keyboards, some words written in Perso-Arabic script were detected as Sanskrit (S) or Hindi (H) words used in Urdu of Hindustan (North India and Pakistan). The hybrid language Urdu is primarily based on using Sanskrit and Hindi words; and it includes other words borrowed from Persian and Arabic languages. Hindustan is the naturally rich region that was ruled by the Persians and the Arabs for many centuries prior to the Mughal reign (1526-1857 CE); and it is the region where many great philosophers and wise men were born and raised such as Pāṇini, Vishnu-Sharma, Kabir, Gandhi,

⁸- On the change from *Abjd* to *Abtṣ* sequence by *Nasr ibn Asim al-laythi*, see Arabic Brief-Dictionary: *Al-Mu'jam Al-Wajiz* المعجم الوجيز for beginners, Ministry of Education, Cairo, 1994, p.2, at <https://archive.org/details/DRM2981/page/n11/mode/1up>

⁹- See the difference between the two *Abjd* sequences, *ibid*, p.2.

and other bright names. The review of the spelling of many words, from VMS (written with Perso-Arabic and Devanagari scripts) in the two volumes of Urdu, Classical Hindi, and English Dictionary by Platts (1884), led to correcting the values of what, falsely, appears in handwriting as inclined-stroke in one of the glyph cases of the letters of ranks 1, 2, 21, and 22, see table.1. The change from vertical to inclined strokes in these four glyphs represents the **fourth concealment trick**. This work uses the glyphs of VMS in regular form, without some concealment tricks; and all glyphs were drawn by the author. The Urdu alphabet comprises 35 letters, where seven of the 28 *Abjd* ranks have two pronunciation cases (for the *Abjd* ranks 2, 3, 4, 7, 11, 20, and 22). There are also additional eleven letters compound with the letter *h* of *Abjd* rank 5, which are the two cases of *Abjd* ranks 2, 3, 4, 11, and 22; and the second case of *Abjd* rank 20.

Moreover, in order to know which glyph form denotes which letter pronunciation case for each rank, the author reviewed the spelling of many words from VMS in the dictionaries of various Hindustani languages, e.g., Hindi, Sanskrit, Urdu, Sindhi, Punjabi, and Pashto, as well as the Persian language. In table.1, the three columns 11, 12 & 13 demonstrate the equivalent Perso-Arabic, Devanāgarī (Hindi), and Roman script for each glyph, respectively. The last column in table.1 shows examples of words from VMS; where each word includes the corresponding glyph (case) of the letter rank in each row, in order to show its correct identity and pronunciation. This process affirmed that the designer of the cipher of VMS used the original *Abjd* ranks of Sinai and many of the encrypted words are Hindi and/or Sanskrit, which are also used in Urdu.

Furthermore, the scribes omitted the spaces between some words in VMS; e.g., between the pronouns, negation words, or definite articles, and the following words; where each became a prefix of other words (e.g. f.1r₁, f.7r, and f.90v, in table.3). In some cases, this led to the repeat of the letter *ā*, three or four times, in two joined words (e.g., f.3v, f.7r, & f.115r₁, in table.3). Besides, in some cases, the scribes also detached the suffix, or the last letter, of some words and used each as a prefix for the following word (e.g., f.1r₃, in table.3). These actions formed the **fifth concealment trick**. The used Urdu-Hindi pronouns in VMS are: (i) *ham* हम that means “we” or “I” (e.g., rank-5, f.1r, in table.1); *āp* आप that means you (e.g., rank-2, f.53r, in table.1); (ii) *yah* यह (dialect) *yih* यह (e.g., rank-10, f.1r, in table.1), *vah* वह, and *yo* यो (e.g., rank-6 & rank-10, f.1r, in table.1) that each means “this, he, she, or it”; and (iii) *ve* वे that means these, they, or those (e.g., rank-10, f.1r, in table.1). Besides, the negation word *nahī.n* नहीं that means no or not is used in VMS (e.g., rank-14, f.17v, in table.1).

Additionally, **the sixth concealment trick** is that in all the words that end with the second and third cases of *Abjd* rank 1 (*ā*, see table.1), the scribe wrote it above the letter that precedes it in the word, perhaps, in order to give a false impression that it is a kind of vowel-diacritics (e.g., f.8r₁, in table.3). In this regard, in VMS, the sequence of reading the words that are composed of glyphs that are not aligned horizontally is as follows: (i) the upper glyph’s position, in most cases, is at the end of the word (e.g., f.51v, in table.3), and (ii) the cover glyph’s position is at its second leg’s position in the word (e.g. see *Abjd* rank 28, f.90r, in table.1). Besides, Urdu and Hindi languages include short words that each forms a prefix of another long word and both have the same meaning (e.g., rank-25, f.65r, in table.1, & f.115v, in table.3).

The **seventh concealment trick** is that, in some of the frequently used words, the writer used the glyphs of the eleven *Abjd* ranks: 7, 8, 9, 16, 18, 19, 23, and from 25 to 28 —that are used in words borrowed from Persian or Arabic languages— to substitute the seven *Abjd* ranks: 2, 13, 14, 11, 20, 21, and 22, out of the remaining seventeen *Abjd* ranks. Unlike the usual method of shifting the substituted

letters, the designer of the cipher shifted each of these eleven *Abjd* ranks by (plus or minus) 5 places or its multiples in order to substitute, in some words, the other seven *Abjd* ranks. The first six of them are frequently used in VMS, where *Abjd* rank 13 “m” was substituted with four *Abjd* ranks (8, 18, 23, and 28) and *Abjd* rank 14 “n” was substituted with two *Abjd* ranks (9 and 19), and each of the other five *Abjd* ranks was substituted with one *Abjd* rank, as demonstrated in fig.4. This implies that despite the use of 28 *Abjd* ranks, the text of VMS was in fact produced using only seventeen *Abjd* ranks, that are: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 20, 21, 22, and 24. These partial polyalphabetic substitutions transformed the affected Indian and Sanskrit words in the text into either Arabic, Persian, or Pashto words—that are also used in Hindustan but with different meanings— which means, among other things, that the writer chose the words that contain substituted letters very carefully. This also means that the original text of VMS contains mostly Indian and Sanskrit words and the true borrowed words from Persian or Arabic languages without substituted letters are rare in the text. Besides, it was also observed that each of these rare borrowed words begins with a special glyph form (see e.g., rank-1, f.4r & rank-2, f.10r, in table.1). Regarding the eleven letters that are compound with “h” in Urdu or Hindi alphabets, the only found cases in VMS are for the two *Abjd* ranks 2 and 3 (i.e., *bh* and *jh*), that in addition to the many cases of substituting *Abjd* rank 2 “b” with *Abjd* rank 7 “z” (i.e., to become *zh*, or the Persian word *zah*, instead of the Hindi letter *bh*) as part of the seventh concealment trick.

<i>Abjd</i> rank of the written glyph	7		8	9	16	18	19	23	25	26	27	28
The shifted (written) glyph & the meant Perso-Arabic, Roman & Devanāgarī script	𑖦	𑖧	𑖨	𑖩	𑖪	𑖫	𑖬	𑖭	𑖮	𑖯	𑖰	𑖱
	ز, z, ज़	ژ, zh, झ	ح, h, ह	ط, t, त	ع, ā, आ	ص, s, स	ق, q, क	ث, s, स	ذ, z, ज़	ض, z, ज़	ظ, z, ज़	غ, gh, ग
Shift value	-5	-5	+5	+5	-5	-5	-5	-(5*2)	-5	-5	-5	-(5*3)
<i>Abjd</i> rank of the substituted glyph	2	2	13	14	11	13	14	13	20	21	22	13
The substituted glyph & the meant Perso-Arabic, Roman & Devanāgarī script	𑖠	𑖡	𑖨	𑖩	𑖪	𑖫	𑖬	𑖭	𑖮	𑖯	𑖰	𑖱
	ب, b, ब	پ, p, प	م, m, म	ن, n, न	ک, k, क	م, m, म	ن, n, न	م, m, म	ر, r, ر	ش, sh, श/ष	ت, t, त	م, m, म

Figure.4: *Abjd* ranks of both the shifted and substituted glyphs in VMS (MS-408); (i) the upper three rows show the twelve glyphs and scripts of the shifted (written) eleven *Abjd* ranks, (ii) the row in the middle shows the shift value(s), and (iii) the lower three rows show the eight glyphs and scripts of the seven substituted *Abjd* ranks.

Despite the use of the ranks of *Abjd* sequence, it is hard to affirm that the original text was written with Perso-Arabic script (i.e., from right to left). Taking into account that Hindi and Urdu languages have the same grammatical structure and share at least 70% of their vocabulary, most likely, VMS’s text was just the output of mapping the Devanāgarī script of a Hindi text into *Abjd* ranks, using the created glyphs. The encryption of the VMS’s text with *Abjd* ranks indicates that the designer was—a descendant of—a Hindustani citizen, may be from Karachi or from the minorities of any of the Indian provinces that were using Perso-Arabic script, such as Oudh (Awadh) in Uttar Pradesh; and he was aware about the two writing systems. Besides, Devanāgarī script have been designed with a condition to include at least 12 vowel-diacritics. For instance, the transliteration of few VMS glyphs to Devanāgarī script showed that each represents, or includes, a vowel diacritic such as one or two of the

vertical strokes of *Abjd* rank 1 that denotes *i* or *ii* (=ī), respectively (see rank-1, in table.1). It is also used instead of the first half circle in some glyphs of *Abjd* ranks 3, 4, 11 and 16 (see table.2), which denotes that each is preceded by the vowel *i*, or *i* follows the previous consonant (e.g., *bid* = pit, f.113v, in table.3).

Moreover, there is no special glyph (or design element) in VMS for the vowel diacritic *o* or *u* to follow the first consonant in the words that begin with, or are composed of, two consonants; it appears only in the transliterations using, e.g., Perso-Arabic or Devanāgarī script (e.g., *but*, f.22r, in table.3). Besides, in VMS, the glyph of *Abjd* rank 6, which is the long vowel *o* or *u*, appears in most cases as the first or last letter in the encoded words (e.g., rank-6, f.1r, in table.1; f.68r₃, in table.3). Similarly, in VMS, there are no special forms of glyphs for the Devanāgarī vowel diacritics *e*, *ē*, *ai*, and *m/ñ* (see, e.g., f.1r, in table.3 & rank-14, f.17v, in table.1). However, in few observed cases in VMS, the vowel *e* was denoted with the glyph of *Abjd* rank 10 in writing the pronoun *we* वे (=they), perhaps, in order to match its equivalent written form using the Perso-Arabic script (see, rank-10, f.1r, in table.1). In the 78 glyphs of VMS that were reviewed so far, the only two cases that include separate vertical stroke(s) are in *Abjd* rank 21 (*sh* with one stroke) and *Abjd* rank 22 (*t* with two strokes); the rest of the cases are either the vowel *i* or *ī* (=ii). In this regard, despite that the strokes that denote the vowels *i* or *ī* can be dealt with as *Abjd* rank 10, for consistency in writing the glyphs, this work dealt with the strokes that denote these two vowels as *Abjd* rank 1, i.e., as vertical strokes instead of inclined strokes. Besides, it is highly unlikely that an inclined stroke of ten replaces the half circle that denotes one in some glyph cases (e.g., f.113v, in table.3).

VMS's text also contains few glyph cases that are not well written, and that give a false impression that they might be additional symbols different from the 108 glyphs that are listed in table.2. The scribal mistakes in writing few glyph cases in VMS (e.g., the compound glyph of *Abjd* ranks "15,2,5" in f.1r, that reads as "*bhas*" भस (H) = descend into water, see table.2) most likely were either a kind of grandiloquence to increase the tricks, or due to lack of concentration, and not because of forgetting the correct glyph forms.

4. The core subject of VMS (MS-408)

Based on the review of the sentences in many pages of VMS, it is clear that although the majority of words in VMS are either Sanskrit or Hindi, the structure of all sentences—that each forms a line—do not follow any Hindustani grammar rules, i.e., the words are misplaced and most sentences lack the necessary prepositions and conjunction words, as well as the verb "to be". Yet, the words of some of these scrambled sentences seem were written (organized) as poetry like spells. In order to get the correct meaning of each sentence, the reader has to rearrange the location of some words and add the missing prepositions, conjunction words, and/or the verb "to be". Each sentence was written like a puzzle, which appears in the first glance as nonsense and this puzzling idea forms the ***eighth concealment trick***. Changing the places of words in each sentence added a kind of difficulty to understand the intended meaning, particularly with the use of many old Sanskrit words that have become no longer in use.

Regarding the name of VMS's writer, narrator, or to whom the text belongs, as shown in box.1, the last sentence in the first paragraph in page f.1r says, "these are the chatters of, someone his name or nickname is, *Bido*". The sentence is written as "*we bak Bido*" = "these/they chatters *Bido*", where the word *bak* बक is the short form of *bakavas* बकवास or *bakbak* बकबक, and the three words mean chatter, gossip, nonsense, or idle talk. And *Bido* बिडो is also a name of a village in Jharkhand state, India.

Box.1: Translation of a short-scrambled sentence from VMS (MS-408, f.1r, line-5)

१४ अ२ वा॒त्त॑१

वे बक बिडो।

we bak Bido.

وی بک بیڈو

These chatter Bido.

[Retrieved sentence]

१४ वा॒त्त॑१ २॥ अ२ ०

वे बिडो की बक हैं।¹⁰

we Bido kī bak hai.n.

They are Bido's chatters.

Unfortunately, the title page of VMS is missing, but the short-scrambled sentence in the last page (f.116v) —that is written beside a Jackal and a naked woman— is transliterated as shown in box-2, and can be translated after rearranging the positions of words and adding the missing prepositions as “Chatter on shocking tricks”.

Box.2: Translation of the last scrambled sentence in VMS (MS-408, f.116v)

अ२ ०२ त्त्त॑॑१

बक हक दाव।

bak hak daāv.

بک ہک داؤ

Chatter shock tricks.

[Retrieved sentence]

त्त्त॑॑१ २॥ ०२ २१ अ२

दाव की हक पर बक।¹¹

daāv kī hak par bak.

Chatter on shocking tricks.

In nearly all pages of VMS we read the two words “*ye but*” (rank-22, f.1r, in table.1), where *ye* means “these” and *but* means “idol(s), fetish(es), or the beloved one; and it is also used as a metaphor to denote the beloved woman in Hindustani poetry”. The glyph of the word *but* can also be read as *bīr* (= brave, warrior, a divine being of female origin, or a man’s own wife among the *Jāṭs* people in North-west India), which is based on dealing with the two vertical strokes in the letter *t* as the vowel *ī* followed by *r*; hence, in this work the word *but* (=idol) will be used to denote a beloved woman and/or a beloved female angel. For instance, in page f.66r, the short sentence (a verse) beside a naked man lying on his back is transliterated and can be translated as shown in box.3.

¹⁰- Synonym of the short word in bold: वे बिडो की **बकबक** हैं।

¹¹- Synonym of the short word in bold: दाव की हक पर **बकबक**।

Box.3: Translation of a scrambled sentence beside a naked man from VMS (MS-408, f.66r)

० ११ ८८० ८ १११४ ८ ११११ १ १११ ८८८ ८८८८

हम जाह ये बुत चमू वम आप चाड़।

Ham cāh ye but camu wam āp cār.

بم چاه يه بت چمو وم آپ چاڑ¹²

We want these idols army spring you love.

[Retrieved sentence]

० ११ ८ १११४ २११ ८ ११११ १ ८८० ८ १११ ८८८ ८८८८ २८ १११ ०

हम ये बुत की चमू जाह और आप चाड़ का वम हैं।¹³

Ham ye but kī camu cāh āur āp cār kā wam hai.n.

We want an army of idols, and you are the spring of love.

The first four words mean “we want these idols”, respectively. The last four words are: *cāmu* = army, division, part (S), *āp* = you (H), *cār* = love (S), and *wam* = path, way, spring of water, or eject (in Sanskrit) or a term to address God Siva (in Hindi). The second letter *m* (*Abjd* rank 13) in the word *wam* was substituted with *h* (*Abjd* rank 8) to become *wah*. In the two parts of the sentence, the writer changed the position of two words: the verb *chah* (= want) and the noun *wam* (= spring), and omitted the preposition *kī* or *kā* (= of), the conjunction word *āur* (= and), and the verb *hai.n* (= are).

Moreover, in the introductory page f.1r, see box.4, the first scrambled sentence in the second paragraph that begins with a cross-section of an opened book —marked in red— declares that the chatters in VMS are that of the talkative Idols about the path of the great blazing fire.

Box.4: Translation of a scrambled sentence from the introductory page of VMS (MS-408, f.1r, line-6)

० ८ १२ ८१ ८२० २ १११ ० १० १८ १२ ८२० १११ ० १११४ ८८० ८ १२१

है ये बक जो डहर मह वह वे बक दहक मह बुत दह ये बककू।

Hai ye bak jo dahar mah vah we bak dahak mah but dah ye bakku.

ہے یہ بک جو ڈہر مہ وہ وی بک دہک مہ بت دہ یہ بکو

Are these chatters that path (route) great these that (they) chatter blazing great idol fire these talkative.

[Retrieved sentence]

१८ ८ १११ ० ८ १११ १२१ १११४ २११ १२ ० ८ ११ १० ८ १११ ० २११ ८८० ८२० २ ८२० १११ २११ १२ ०

वे ये मह और बककू बुत की बक हैं। जो वह ये मह की दह दहक के डहर की बक है।¹⁴

we ye mah āur bakku but kī bak hai.n. jo vah ye mah kī dah dahak ke dahar kī bak hai.

They are the chatters of the great talkative idols, which they are chatters about the path to the great blazing fire.

¹²- The pronoun *ye* ये (=these) is the plural of *yah* यह (=this) but in Urdu, both are written as یہ.

¹³- Synonyms of old words in bold: हम ये बुत की **सेना चाहिए** और आप **प्रेम का पथ** हैं।

¹⁴- Synonyms of old or short words in bold: वे ये **महान** और **बातूनी** बुत की **बकबक** हैं। जो वह ये **महान** की **ज्वाला** दहक के **रास्ता** की **बकबक** है।

Box.5 demonstrates another scrambled sentence from VMS, which begins with “we talkative burden”. In this regard, Currier¹⁵ (1976) postulated that the first part of the herbal section is written in Language A and the biological section is written in Language B; but box.4 shows a scrambled sentence taken from the first part of the herbal section (page f.1r, line-6) and the sentence in box.5 herein below is taken from the biological section (page f.78v, line-7) and both are the same Hindi language.

Box.5: Translation of a scrambled sentence from the text of VMS (MS-408, f.78v, line-7)

० ११ ०२१ ८८८१ ० ११ ८१ ८८८१ १० ११ ८८१ १० ११ ८१ ० ११ ८१ ० ११ ८१

हम बककू दायो हम अयो दायो भम आयो भम अयो हम बक हम अयो।

ham bakku dāyo, ham āyo dāyo bham āayo bham āyo, ham bak, ham āyo.

ہم بکو دایو، ہم ایو دایو، ہم آیو، ہم ايو، ہم بک، ہم ایو

We talkative burden we revealed burden wander come wander revealed we chatter we revealed (expressed).

[Retrieved sentence]

० ११ ०२१ ८१ ८८८१ ० ८१ ० ११ ८८८१ ८१ २१ १० ०
० ११ ०२ ११ १० ११ ८८१ ० ८१ ० ११ ८१ ८१ ८१ २ ११ १० ११ ०

हम बककू और दायो हैं और हम दायो अयो कर रहे हैं।

हम बक में भमे आयो हैं और हम अयो और अयो के लिए भमे हैं।¹⁶

ham bakku āur dāyo hai.n āur ham dāyo āyo kar rahe hai.n.

ham bak me.n bhame āayo hai.n āur ham āyo āur ke lie bhame hai.n.

We are talkative and burdensome, and we are revealing the burden.

We have wandered in the chatter and we have wandered for appearance and display.

Furthermore, box.6 demonstrates a scrambled sentence written beside a shrub, in page f.65r. It is composed of six words, were *bish* means poison (or poison damsel), *bash* means power, settled, or authority, and *bar* is the short form of *bargad* that both mean Banyan-tree or groom. It is not clear whether the writer of VMS has dealt with the flowering shrub in this page as a talking woman; because in the diagram of Gemini in page f.72r, one of the women, beside a man, says “*ham har bash*” = we all powerful (see, f.72r, in table.3); and if we added the missing *hai.n* = are, at the end, it says “we are all powerful (or settled)”. In the sentence in box.6, the glyphs of the letters *r* (rank 20) and *sh* (rank 21) were substituted with the glyphs of *Abjd* ranks 25 and 26, respectively. And the meaning of the sentence is “we are the poison of these settled banyan trees”. In Hindi, writers some time repeat words or pronouns to accent the meaning, in this sentence the word *bash* is repeated and in another sentence in VMS, the pronoun *ham* (=we/I) was repeated (see f.8r4, in table.3).

¹⁵- See the results of Currier’s analysis at http://www.voynich.nu/extra/curr_main.html

¹⁶- Synonyms of old or short words in bold: हम बातूनी और बोझ हैं और हम बोझ प्रकट कर रहे हैं।
हम बकबक में घुमे आयो हैं और हम प्रकट और प्रकट के लिए घुमे हैं।

In the rest of the introductory page and other pages in VMS, the writer introduces other animals to the chatter such as: a fox-cub “*bir*” (f.1r, in table.3), an iguana “*goh*” (f.6v, in table.3), and a cow “*gā’o*” (f.51r, in table.3). Table.3 shows other examples of Sanskrit and Hindi words, and short scrambled sentences from different pages in VMS.

Moreover, the strange thing in VMS is that the captions of many illustrations are not related to the portrayed topics. For instance, in the three diagrams in page f.68r that give the impression that they record the names of our sun, our moon, and some stars in the sky dome in specific celestial events, the written words beside these celestial bodies seem as parts of an imaginary chatter and have no astronomical meanings. For instance, we read the following. (i) Idol chatter “*but bak*”, in the 1st diagram, beside a star (f.68r₂, in table.3). (ii) the Dutch “*dačo*”, in the 2nd diagram, beside a star (f.68r₃, in table.3). (iii) This talkative “*yah bakku*” in the 3rd diagram, beside the seven small stars (f.68r₄, in table.3). The case is similar in all illustrations in VMS (i.e. astronomical, astrological, botanical, etc.), which may be additional concealment trick.

5. Conclusions

This paper showed that VMS is a cipher text that encodes a mediaeval Hindi language, which most likely was produced by a team composed of the designer of the cipher, the writer(s), the scribes, and the painters. The designer of the cipher—who may have been an Indian polymath—used the grid of the rectangle 6*8 units and its diagonal of 10 units to create almost 78 geometrically assembled glyphs so that each denotes numerically the rank of a specific letter in *Abjd* (*Abjad*) sequence of the trips of Madian of Sinai, from one to twenty-eight. The designer used eight concealment tricks in order to conceal the geometric cipher and the encoded language that are: (i) he used the ranks of *Abjd* sequence instead of the *Abts* sequence, or the sequence of Hindi alphabet, (ii) he topologically modified the geometric proportions of the design-elements of the assembled glyphs. (iii) he changed the inclination of the linear design elements (vertical strokes) in some of the glyphs of *Abjd* ranks 1, 2, 21, and 22, (iv) he changed the last linear design elements into curves in the glyphs of *Abjd* ranks 6, 20, 21, 22, 25 and 26, (v) he omitted the spaces between some words and detached the suffix, or the last letter, of some words and used each as a prefix for the next word, (vi) in the words that end with the glyphs of the second or third cases of *Abjd* rank 1, he wrote it above the glyph (letter) that precedes it in the word, (vii) he used the glyphs of the eleven *Abjd* ranks 7, 8, 9, 16, 18, 19, 23, and from 25 to 28—that are used in words borrowed from Persian or Arabic languages—to substitute in some of the frequently used words the glyphs of seven *Abjd* ranks (eight letters) from the remaining seventeen *Abjd* ranks, and (viii) in each line of the text, he removed most of the prepositions, conjunction words, and/or the verb “to be” and changed the positions of the remaining words to produce partially incomplete scrambled sentences. The production of the final scrambled text of VMS, from the original copy, most likely was based on the production of two other preliminary versions. In each page of the original text, the writer removed most of the prepositions and conjunction words and changed the positions of words in each line, and he wrote the end product as scrambled literary text in the first preliminary version. Then, in a second version, he replaced the original scripts—most likely Devanāgarī—with the new designed glyphs that are based on the sequence of *Abjd* and linked some words together. At last, after drawing the sketches on the parchments of the final version, the scribes copied the lines of the generated ciphered text of the second preliminary version beside the sketches in the final version of VMS, or “the Chatters of Biḍo on the great Idols and the settled Banyan trees”.

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Table.1: The glyphs of VMS (MS-408) and their equivalents in Persian, Devanāgarī, and Roman script, and examples of words from its text. *

Abjd rank	Glyph used in VMS	Numeric values of the assembling parts of the glyphs used in VMS (MS-408)								Pronunciation of the glyph letters: (P/A) Perso-Arabic, (H) Hindi (in Devanāgarī), & (R) Roman			Examples of words from VMS, with Perso-Arabic & Hindi transliterations, Roman pronunciation with vowels, and English meaning. Symbols of languages or origin of words: Hindi (H), Persian (P), Arabic (A), & Sanskrit (S).
		1	1	1	1	1	5	10	10	P/A	H	R	
		د	ذ	ح	ا	ـ	و	ل	/				
1	◌		1							ā/ā	आ/ा	ā	◌◌◌◌ āpā آپا (H)= self, elder sister (f.7v).
	◌	1							ā	अ	ā	◌◌ āp آپ (S) = bad (f.4r).	
	◌			1					ā/ā	आ/ा	ā	◌◌◌ āhak अहक (H) = longing, wish, desire (f.3r)	
	◌								◌	इ/ि	i	◌◌◌ pabi पबि (H) = pub (f.100r)	
2	◌				1				◌	ी	ii=ī	◌◌◌ bik बीक (H) dialect = बिक बिक (H) dialect = wolf (f.104v).	
	◌		1		1				◌	ब	b	◌◌ bak बक (S/H) = idle talk, chatter, nonsense (f.1r).	
	◌	1	1						◌	प	p	◌◌◌ āp آپ (S/H) = you (for respect) (f.53r). ◌◌ pe पे (H) = upon, on (f.1r).	
	◌	2							◌	ब	b	◌◌ bā/bihi बा (P/A) = by, with, in, for (f.10r)	
3	◌		1			1			◌ (with h=भ)	ब (with h=भ)	b (with h=bh)	◌◌◌ bhav भव (S) = life, origin, world (f.15v).	
	◌		1	1		1			◌	ज	j	◌◌ jo जो (S/H) = who, what, which, if (f.1r).	
4	◌		2			1			◌	च	č/ch	◌◌◌ cāh चाह (H) = wish (f.66r).	
	◌	1	2			1			◌	द	d	◌◌◌ dahak दहक (H)= inflamed, burning (f.88v).	
4	◌	1	2			1			◌	ड	ḍ	◌◌◌ ḍā'o दाव (H) dialect = ḍāh दाह = burning (f.1r).	

Abjd rank	Glyph used in VMS	Numeric values of the assembling parts of the glyphs used in VMS (MS-408)							Pronunciation of the glyph letters: (P/A) Perso-Arabic, (H) Hindi (in Devanāgarī), & (R) Roman			Examples of words from VMS, with Perso-Arabic & Hindi transliterations, Roman pronunciation with vowels, and English meaning. Symbols of languages or origin of words: Hindi (H), Persian (P), Arabic (A), & Sanskrit (S).	
		1	1	1	1	1	5	10	10	P/A	H		R
		۱	۱	۱	۱	۱	۵	۱۰	۱۰				
5	◦						5			ھ/و	ह	h	◦ ^{۱۱} <i>ham</i> هـ هم (H) = we, I (f.1r, f105r).
6	۹				1		5			و و/و	व/वु/ वू/वो	w/v	۹ ^۰ <i>wah</i> و वह (H) = ۹ ^۰ <i>ho</i> هو वो (Bhojpūrī dialect) = that thing, that person, the, those, they, he, she, it (f.1r).
7 (=2)	۹				1	1	5			= ز **ب	ज़= ब	z=b	۹ ^۰ <i>bha</i> به भ (H)= fourth Indian letter; or <i>bah</i> به बह = flow, cart, nomadic tribe (f.1r)-
	۹				1	1	5			= ژ **ب	झ= प	zh= p	۹ ^۰ <i>āpak</i> آبک अपक (S) = water, liquid (f.20v).
8 (=13)	۱۱				2	1	5			= ح **م	ह= म	h= m	◦ ^{۱۱} <i>ham</i> هـ هم (H) = we, I (f.1r).
9 (=14)	۱۴				2	2	5			= ط **ن	ت= ن	t= n	۱۴ ^۰ <i>nah</i> نه (H)= nail (f.6r).
10	8						2*5			ی	य	y	8 ^۰ <i>yah</i> به यह (H) = 8 ^۰ <i>yo</i> يو यो dialect (H) = this (f.1r); and ۹ ⁸ <i>we</i> وى वे (H) = these, they, that (f.1r).
11	۲	1						10		ک	क	k	۲۰۲ <i>kuhuk</i> كهك كوهك (H)= cry, scream (f.115v).
	۱۱		2		2	2	5			گ	ग	g	۱۱ ^۰ <i>gahak</i> گهك गहक (H)= joyous emotion, pleasure (f.99r).
12	۱۲		2		2	3	5			ل	ल	l	۱۲ ^۰ <i>lau</i> لو लौ (H) = candle flam, hope, longing (f.11r).
	۱۲				4	3	5			ل	ल	l	۱۲ ^۰ <i>luć</i> لُج لُح (H)= naked (f.14r).
13	۱۳				2	1	2*5			م	म	m	۱۳ ^۰ <i>mach</i> مچ मछ (H)= fish (f.8r).
	۱۳		3		2	3	5			م	म	m	۱۳ ^۰ <i>mah</i> مه मह (P)= great (f.1r).
14	۱۴				2	2	2*5			ن	न	n	۱۴ ^۰ <i>nahii.n</i> نهیں نہی (S)= no, not, a negation (f.17v).

Abjd rank	Glyph used in VMS	Numeric values of the assembling parts of the glyphs used in VMS (MS-408)							Pronunciation of the glyph letters: (P/A) Perso-Arabic, (H) Hindi (in Devanāgarī), & (R) Roman			Examples of words from VMS, with Perso-Arabic & Hindi transliterations, Roman pronunciation with vowels, and English meaning. Symbols of languages or origin of words: Hindi (H), Persian (P), Arabic (A), & Sanskrit (S).	
		1	1	1	1	1	5	10	10	P/A	H		R
		د	ك	ح	ا	ـ	و	ـ	/				
15	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡		1		2	2	2*5			س	स	s	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡 <i>ās</i> اس अस (S)= this type, similar, equivalent (f.8r)
16 (=11)	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠		2		2	2	2*5			=ع **ك	अ/, क	ā/, k	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠 <i>kabk</i> كَبِك كَبْك (P)= partridge bird, chukor (f.8r). (or कब के
17	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠		2		2	3	2*5			ف	फ	f	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠 <i>fāw</i> فَاو فَاو (P/A) = striking (f.7r); & <i>fāv</i> فَاو = jump.
18 (=13)	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠		3		2	3	2*5			=ص **م	स= म	ṣ=m	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>mahak</i> مَهَك مَهَك (H)= fragrance, smell, flavor, or effect (f.1r).
19 (=14)	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠		4		2	3	2*5			=ق **ن	क =न	q =n	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>nāv</i> نَاو نَاو (P)= a boat, a ship; or a river, a drain, channel, aqueduct, canal (f.80r); & <i>nāvan</i> नाव (S)= description.
20	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠							10	10	ر	र	r	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>bar</i> بَر بَر (H)= choosing, but, moreover, Indian fig tree (f.36r).
	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠						2*5	10		ڑ	ड़	r	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>cār</i> چَار چَاڑ (H)= mark, love (f.66r).
21	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠				1			10	10	ش	श or ष	sh	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>bash</i> بَش بَش (S)= subservient, dominance, authority, power (f.75r).
	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠					1		10	10	ش	श or ष	sh	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>shabak</i> شَبَك شَبَك (A/Pr)= nets, lattice, to make reticulated (f.55r).
22	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠				2			10	10	ت	त	t	8 𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>ye but</i> يَه بَت يَه بُوत (H)= these idols (metaphorically means these beloved women, in Hindi poetry) (f.1r).
	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠		1		3	3	3*5			ت	त	t	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>tučā</i> تُچَا تُچَا = <i>lučā</i> لُچَا (H) = low, bad, base (f.100v-101r).
	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠				1	1		10	10	ٹ	ट	t	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>caṭ</i> چَٹ چَٹ (H)= quickly, a sound, wholly, eating up (f.66r).
23 (=13)	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠				4	4	3*5			=ٹ **م	स= म	ṣ=m	𐎧𐎠𐎢𐎡𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠𐎠 <i>macā.u</i> مَچَاؤ مَچَاؤ (H) = the doer (f.87v).

Abjd rank	Glyph used in VMS	Numeric values of the assembling parts of the glyphs used in VMS (MS-408)							Pronunciation of the glyph letters: (P/A) Perso-Arabic, (H) Hindi (in Devanāgarī), & (R) Roman			Examples of words from VMS, with Perso-Arabic & Hindi transliterations, Roman pronunciation with vowels, and English meaning. Symbols of languages or origin of words: Hindi (H), Persian (P), Arabic (A), & Sanskrit (S).		
		1	1	1	1	1	5	10	10	P/A	H		R	
		د	ك	ح	ل	ـ	و	ـ	/					
24			2		3	4	3*5				خ	ख	kh	<i>kho</i> خو खो or <i>khoo</i> खू (P)= nature, way, custom (f.86v).
25 (=20)							5	10	10	= ذ ** ر	ज़ = र	z = r	<i>bar</i> بر बर (H) = <i>bargad</i> برگد बरगद = Banyan Tree, Indian fig tree (f.65r).	
26 (=21)					1		5	10	10	= ض ** ش	ज़ = श	z = sh	<i>bash</i> بش बश (S)= subservient, dominance, authority, power (f.65r).	
27 (=22)					4	3	4*5			= ظ ** ت	ज़ = ट	z = t	Unused in the text; it appeared in just one diagram (f.57v).	
28 (=13)			4		4	5	3*5			= غ ** م	घ/ग = म	gh/g = m	<i>ye bamav</i> ये बमव (H)= these vomit (f.90r).	

* In this work the used font of VMS’s glyphs is regular, hence the following remarks should be taken into consideration: (a) some concealment tricks were omitted, which are: (i) the inclination of the vertical stroke in the letters *sh* & *t*, and what denotes the vowels *i* and *ii* (=ī); (ii) the end curves in the letters *v*, *r*, *f*, *sh*, *t*, *z*, & *z*; and (iii) the topological increase in the diameter of the upper half-circle in the glyphs of the letters *k* & *p*. (b) the modifications in the glyph forms that were kept consistent with what in VMS are: (i) the topological decrease in the diameter of the circle of five units; (ii) the topological increase in the lengths of some of the horizontal or vertical strokes of one unit; and (iii) the topological decrease in the lengths of the inclined strokes of ten units.

** Glyphs of letters that substitute other letters in VMS based on the shifting by 5 places or its multiples (+ or -).

Table.2: The used Glyphs of *Abjd* ranks in VMS's text (MS-408).*

<i>Abjd</i> ranks of single glyphs			
1	2	3	4
ⲓ ⲛ ⲁ ⲓ	ⲁ ⲛ ⲛ ⲛ ⲛ	ⲛ ⲛ ⲛ ⲛ	ⲛ ⲛ ⲛ ⲛ
5	6	7	8
ⲟ	ⲑ ⲑ	ⲑ ⲑ ⲛ	ⲑⲑ
9	10	11	12
ⲑⲑ	ⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲛ ⲛ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲛ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲛ
13	14	15	16
ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ
17	18	19	20
ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲛ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲛ ⲛ ⲛ
21	22	23	24
ⲛ ⲛ ⲛ	ⲛ ⲛ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲛ	ⲑⲑ
25	26	27	28
ⲛ	ⲛ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ
<i>Abjd</i> ranks of samples of compound glyphs			
1,7,1	1,2	2,1	2,5
ⲑⲑ	ⲛ	ⲛ	ⲛ ⲛ
2,25	3,2	3,5	3,6
ⲛ ⲛ	ⲛ ⲛ	ⲛ	ⲛ ⲛ
3,17 (or 19)	6,1	7,1	7,5
ⲑⲑ	ⲛ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ
7,6	7,5,1	7,1,8	7,9
ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ
10,2 (or 2,7,3)	10,2 (or 8,2,2)	10,6 (or 2,6,8)	1,7,11
ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ
12,2 (or 13 **)	15,5 (or 13,2,5)	15,6 (or 2,6,13)	15,2,5
ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ
16,2 (or 17 **)	17,2 (or 18 **)	22,1	4, 28
ⲑⲑ	ⲑⲑ	ⲛ ⲛ	ⲑⲑ ⲑⲑ

* The cells in gray color demonstrate the ranks of the glyphs that substitute eight of the remaining glyphs, as shown in fig.4, and their rank values are written in bold font.

** The contentious lower horizontal stroke equals one because there is no change in direction.

Table.3: Examples of short scrambled sentences and words from VMS (MS 408).*

Page	words from VMS (MS 408)	Transliteration/Translation			English meaning of each word in the scrambled sentences
		Peso-Arabic	Roman (with vowels) <i>ā=aa, ć=ch & w=v</i>	Devanāgarī	
f.1r1	8 a1v o2 ffco 8q	یسے بر یک ماہ یو	<i>ye bir hak mah yo</i>	ये बिर हक माह यो	These fox-cubs/virtue surprise moon (or beloved) this.
f.1r2	o ff o2 8 a11v	ہم ہر یہ بیت	<i>ham har ye bit</i>	हम हर ये बित	We every these verses
f.1r3	q ff o2	وم ہپ	<i>wam hap</i>	वम अप	Way bad/opposite
f.2r	8o2c2o2q	یہ کچھ کو	<i>yah kuch ko</i>	यह कुछ को	This some
f.3v	2c c2c	پا آپ	<i>pā āp</i>	पा आप	You get it (or get you)
f.5v	c2o2	چاہک	<i>ćahak</i>	चाहक	Longing, a lover
f.6v	ffqo	گوہ	<i>goh</i>	गोह	Iguana, lizard, Gangetic alligator
f.7r	8cc c2c	یاء آپا	<i>yā āpā</i>	यआ आपा	Elder sister's nick
f.8r1	o ff a11v	ہم بیتا	<i>ham bitā</i>	हम बिता	We/I spent
f.8r2	2 c2o2 2 a12	پہ چہر پہ بش	<i>pe ćhar pe bish</i>	पे छर पे बिष	On deception (and) on poison
f.8r3	8c2o 8 a11v	یچہ یہ بت	<i>yaćah ye but</i>	यचह ये बुत	Yea these idols/ beloved (women)
f.8r4	o ff o ff c2o 8&	ہم ہم چہ یڑ	<i>ham ham ćah yar</i>	हम हम चह यड़	We (are) stubborn
f.11v	ffcv	مار	<i>mār</i>	मार	Beat, kill
f.15v1	c2o2	چہک	<i>ćahak</i>	चहक	Chirping of birds, warble, whistle
f.15v2	c2q	بہو	<i>bhava</i>	भव	Life/existing
f.17v	8o 12	یہ اک	<i>yah ik (iek)</i>	यह ऐक	This one
f.19r	ff c2 o2	سچ ہک	<i>sac hak</i>	सच हक	True shock
f.22r	ff o 8 a11v	نہ یہ بت	<i>nah ye but</i>	नह ये बुत	Nail these idols/ beloved (women)
f.24v	22	2 بک	<i>2 bak/buk</i>	२ बक	2 Chatters
f.39r	ff8q	گیو	<i>gayo</i>	गयो	Gone
f.51r	ffc2q	گاؤ	<i>gā'o = gāv</i>	गाव	Bull, ox, or cow
f.51v	q ff a2	بن بر (بن برگد)	<i>ban bar (ban bargad)</i>	बन बर (बन बरगद)	Forest Banyan-tree
f.55v	a1v	پر	<i>bir</i>	बिर	A Fox-cub, virtue

Page	words from VMS (MS 408)	Transliteration/Translation			English meaning of each word in the scrambled sentences
		Peso-Arabic	Roman (with vowels) <i>ā=aa, ć=ch & w=v</i>	Devanāgarī	
f.58r	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	بهن بیش	Bhan bīsh	भन बीष	Too much buzzing
f.65v	𐌆𐌱𐌰	بک	<i>bik = bīk</i>	बिक = बीक	Wolf/jackal
f.66r	𐌆𐌱𐌰	کب	<i>kab</i>	कब	When
f.68r ₁	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	بت بک	<i>but bak</i>	बुत बक	Idol/beloved chatter
f.68r ₂	𐌆𐌱𐌰	ڈچو	<i>ḍačo</i>	डचो	The Dutch
f.68r ₃	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	یه بکو	<i>yah bakku</i>	यह बककू	This talkative
f.72r	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	هم هر بیش	ham har bash	हम हर बश	We every authority, or We all strong
f.78r	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	سہک بر	<i>Sahak bir</i>	सहक बरि	Misguided fox-cub
f.78v ₁	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	سوم ایو	Som ayo	सोम अयो	God-of-Moon come
f.78v ₂	𐌆𐌱𐌰	دایو	<i>dāyo</i>	दायो	Burden
f.85v- f.86r	𐌆𐌱𐌰	دیو	<i>Dio = daiā</i>	दयो = दया	Gift, give, generous, compassionate
f.90v	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	میں دھپ	<i>main dhap</i>	में धप	In loss (in blow)
f.113v	𐌆𐌱𐌰	بد	<i>bid</i>	बिद	A pit into which children in play endeavor to throw balls or marbles
f.115r ₁	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	ہا آپ	<i>hā āp</i>	हा आप	Yes you
f.115r ₂	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	بہام	bhām	भाम	The Sun
f.115v	𐌆𐌱𐌰 𐌆𐌱𐌰	بک بک	<i>bak bak = bak</i>	बकबक = बक	Chatter, gossip, talk too much
f.116r	𐌆𐌱𐌰	داڑ = داڑھ	<i>daār=daārḥ</i>	दाड़ = दाढ़	A jaw tooth, molar

* The cells in gray color demonstrate the pages and the words that contain substituted letters (glyphs); and the substituted letters are written in bold font in the column of the Roman script.

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It will be added later